

OSM Science 2025: Diversifying the Study of OpenStreetMap

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The first Academic Track of State of the Map (SotM) was organized at SotM 2018 in Milan, Italy. Since then, it has been held regularly, continuing even during the Covid-19 pandemic. In 2023, the track was hosted within SotM EU and renamed OSM Science to emphasize its role as the only academic meeting dedicated exclusively to research on and with OpenStreetMap (OSM). From 2018 to 2023, the hosting locations—Milan, Italy; Heidelberg, Germany; Florence, Italy; and Antwerp, Belgium (with Cape Town omitted, as SotM 2020 was moved online due to the pandemic)—all lay within Central Europe. This concentration reflects broader publication patterns, as most OSM-related academic papers are authored by scholars based in Europe [1]. The 2024 and 2025 editions, however, mark a departure from this trend, with OSM Science following SotM to Nairobi, Kenya in 2024 and Manila, the Philippines in 2025. These shifts create a unique opportunity to explore the implications of expanding OSM Science to new regions. They raise important questions about whether holding the meeting outside Europe alters the nature of the event and whether such moves influence representation—shaping who authors contributions, what topics are investigated, and which case study locations are highlighted. This must also take into account the growing role of remote participation, normalized during the Covid-19 years.

Across all editions of the Academic Track/OSM Science [2–6], 96 abstracts have been published (excluding 2018, which released no proceedings, and including the forthcoming 2024 edition). Europe and North America dominate, with individuals affiliated to institutions there authoring between 60% and 94% of abstracts (mean 83%; counts include co-authorship across continents). Asian institutions appear in four of seven editions—peaking at 30% in 2020 and 2025—while African institutions appear in only three: 2020 (30%), 2023 (6%), and 2024 (9%). The unusually high African share in 2020 reflects the

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original plan to host SotM in Cape Town, though the event shifted online. Regional imbalance has in fact deepened: during the Covid and immediate post-Covid years (2020–2023), Europe/North America’s share rose from 60% to 94%, despite remote presentation lowering formal barriers. The 2021 edition, designed from the outset as online, included no Asian or African authors. Only when the conference moved outside Europe did the share of Europe/North America decline—to 91% in 2024 (Kenya) and 80% in 2025 (Philippines). Geography therefore continues to matter: hosting in new regions demonstrably increases the visibility of underrepresented voices.

The question is whether shifts in participation also influence content. One indicator is the geography of case studies. The editions with the highest shares of African or Asian case studies are 2020 (50%) and 2024 (37%)—the two African editions. This aligns with a broader pattern: authors generally study locations close to home [1]. Across all editions (including 2025), only 17% of European or North American authors addressed African or Asian case studies, compared with 60% among African and Asian authors. A second indicator is research focus. We classified abstracts into four categories: (1) basic OSM research—implementation and data quality; (2) OSM-oriented research—studies of contribution patterns, contributors, or tools to guide mapping; (3) social research—analyses of OSM’s societal impact and context; and (4) reviews (one abstract, omitted from analysis). Over time, basic research dominates, OSM-oriented work declines, and social research grows, with little connection to conference location. Differences by author affiliation, however, are more striking. Among European and North American authors, basic (43%) and OSM-oriented (39%) work are balanced. Among African and Asian authors, basic research is far more prevalent (67%) and OSM-oriented much less so (20%). This suggests a structural gap: in the Global North, data quality and implementation are increasingly seen as “solved,” with attention shifting to machine learning and GeoAI; elsewhere, foundational challenges remain pressing. Expanding representation therefore potentially enriches OSM Science by reintroducing perspectives that highlight persistent blind spots in mainstream discourse.

The 2025 abstracts illustrate how origins shape the agenda. Among European and North American contributions, work spans the full range of research. In basic OSM research, Schultz et al. [7] introduce OSMLanduse, the first EU-wide 10 m land-use dataset, harmonizing OSM semantics with Sentinel-2 imagery through deep learning, achieving high accuracy and offering a reproducible framework for continental mapping (classified as European despite Asian co-authors, as the lead and most authors are Europe-based). Williams & Priestnal [8] present PlaceCrafter, which uses OSM POI data to generate platial regions that reflect how people use space, supporting more flexible regional analysis. Zohar et al. [9] develop a geocoding framework integrating OSM and GeoNames to localize wildfire-related tweets during the 2016 Haifa fire, demonstrating OSM’s multilingual, fine-grained features as critical for hyperlocal monitoring. Kašík [10] contributes a city-scale extrinsic quality assessment for Brno, revealing the limits of ISO 19157 for qualitative attributes while offering an alternative pathway for municipal-level OSM quality assessment.

OSM-oriented studies include Štampach et al.’s [11] user testing of the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team’s (HOT) fAIr tool, showing that manual mapping in JOSM was superior overall but also highlighting fAIr’s accessibility for beginners and potential as a complementary tool. Similarly, Herrera-Murillo et al. [12] analyze HOT Tasking Manager projects, identifying uncoordinated individual mapping by beginners as dominant and suggesting design improvements to better support collaboration.

In social research, Mooney et al. [13] examine how major LLMs and chatbots portray OSM, finding generally positive sentiment—emphasizing openness, coverage, and community—while also noting concerns about uneven quality and completeness. Nguyen et al. [14] describe EUthMappers, an ERASMUS+ project embedding OSM-based mapping into STEM education across five European countries, engaging secondary students in humanitarian mapping and demonstrating OSM’s role in education and civic engagement.

By contrast, Asian contributions focus on basic OSM research. Ahmed [15] develops an unsupervised machine learning framework to assess OSM data quality in Dhaka, clustering contributors based on behavioral metadata and showing that activity, thematic focus, and spatial distribution strongly predict reliability. Maliha [16] produces accessibility maps for disaster preparedness in Dhaka, identifying safe open spaces and building a routing model using OSM roads and buildings.

The 2025 edition thus reflects topic-related trends across earlier years. Yet beyond the absence of OSM-oriented and social research in the Asian abstracts, deeper contrasts emerge in motivation and method. For example, Kašík’s [10] quality assessment assumes the availability of authoritative data, while Ahmed [15] addresses contexts where such data are scarce. Similarly, the implementation-oriented study differs both in aims and techniques: Maliha [16] is motivated by urgent local needs, whereas Schultz et al. [7] and Williams & Priestnal [8] develop more generic systems. European and North American authors employ advanced methods such as deep learning [7], fuzzy clustering [8], and NLP [9], while Asian contributions rely on established approaches such as K-Means clustering, Principal Component Analysis [15] and network analysis [16].

Notably, all three Asian abstracts [15,16] were authored by scholars based in Bangladesh. This pattern is not unique: all South American contributions across past editions originated in Brazil, largely from a single research group. While this concentration limits the robustness of comparative analysis, it illustrates how holding OSM Science outside Europe can support nascent research groups by exposing their members to broader trends and facilitating interaction with established teams. To realize this potential, however, gaps in motivation and methods need to be bridged. This remains constrained: only 6 (43%) of the abstracts authored by African and Asian researchers included European or North American co-authors. Another challenge lies in ensuring physical participation: only 30% of the 2025 talks were delivered in person, compared with 60% in 2024 and 71% in 2023. Diversifying conference locations creates opportunities for new voices, but sustained progress requires stronger infrastructures for fostering collaboration and supporting researcher mobility—not only from Europe and North America outward, but also in the reverse direction. Despite technological advances that have reduced barriers to remote interaction, our analysis underscores that structural constraints on mobility and collaboration remain pressing challenges, not only for OSM Science meetings but for the field as a whole.

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